

Fast Frequency Characterization of Inductive Voltage Transformers using Damped Oscillatory Waves

Gabriella Crotti, Giovanni D'Avanzo, Antonio Delle Femine, Daniele Gallo, *Member, IEEE*,
Claudio Iodice, Carmine Landi, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Palma S. Letizia, Mario Luiso, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Measurements of harmonics and, in general, of power quality in distribution grids are becoming more and more an essential task, due to the proliferation of switching power devices. Instrument Transformers (ITs), that are necessary for these kind of measurements in distribution grids, in turns, need to be frequency characterized. Although international standards about ITs do not suggest procedures for their frequency characterization, there are some characterization procedures that are acknowledged in scientific literature. They are based on the application of realistic power system waveforms to the ITs, in order to test their behaviour in conditions very similar to the actual operating conditions. A drawback of these procedures is the quite long duration of the tests, in the order of $\sim 1 - 10$ hours. Therefore, this paper proposes a new waveform for the frequency characterization of inductive Voltage Transformers (VTs), composed by the superposition of a fundamental component and a periodic transient phenomenon, namely a damped sine wave. With its use, it is possible, with a single waveform, to evaluate the frequency behaviour of an inductive VT, thus with a test duration in the order of ~ 1 s. The waveform is theoretically analysed and experimentally applied to two commercial VTs for medium voltage distribution grids. Results are compared with those obtained with the IT frequency characterization methods most acknowledged in scientific literature.

Index Terms—Instrument Transformers, Inductive Voltage Transformers, Harmonics, Interharmonics, Transient Phenomena, Damped Oscillatory Waves

I. INTRODUCTION

Harmonics are recognized as one of the most critical Power Quality (PQ) phenomena due to their significant increase in recent years and the numerous issues they can cause. The main sources of harmonics are the switching power converters

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Gabriella Crotti and Palma Sara Letizia are with the Divisione Metrologia dei materiali innovativi e scienze della vita, Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica, 10135 Turin, Italy (e-mail: p.letizia@inrim.it).

Giovanni D'Avanzo is with the Dipartimento Tecnologie di trasmissione e distribuzione (TTD), Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico S.p.A., 20134 Milan, Italy, (e-mail: giovanni.davanzo@rse-web.it).

Antonio Delle Femine, Daniele Gallo, Claudio Iodice, Mario Luiso and Carmine Landi are with the Dipartimento di Ingegneria, Università degli Studi della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli," 81031 Aversa, Italy (e-mail: mario.luiso@unicampania.it).

widely used in renewable power plants, energy storage facilities and High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) systems [1]. The energy transition is promoting the use of these devices in distribution grids, making harmonics a crucial issue also at Medium Voltage (MV) level.

The growing emphasis on monitoring harmonics has led to the publication of several international standards. These standards establish limits for harmonics [2], prescribe methods and indices for measuring them [3] and provide accuracy limits and guidelines for the characterization of PQ instruments (PQIs) [4]-[8]. PQIs are designed and built with standardised low input voltage levels. Therefore, measuring harmonics at MV level requires transducers to reduce voltage to levels compatible with the PQIs input stage. This task is very commonly assigned to inductive Instrument Transformers (ITs), namely Voltage and Current Transformers (VTs and CTs), already installed in MV grids for metering and/or protection applications. However, due to a lack of international standards dealing with the characterization of ITs at frequencies different from the power frequency (50/60 Hz), typically, the installed VTs and CTs are characterized only at 50/60 Hz, even if they are used to measure PQ phenomena, that can range up to several kilohertz.

In fact, although a number of international standards deal with limits for PQ disturbances in public distribution systems, measurement of PQ and characterization of PQIs, the standards on Instrument Transformers (mainly the IEC 61869 standard family [9]-[12]) give accuracy specifications and procedures for the characterization only at power frequency. Instead, at higher frequencies, only accuracy limits are given; in particular, the IEC 61869-1 Ed. 2 [9], published very recently, gives accuracy specifications up to 500 kHz.

For what concerns the scientific literature, in recent years a number of papers dealt with the characterization of ITs, both inductive and Low Power ITs (LPITs), up to several kilohertz [13]-[26]; for sake of brevity, here only some papers are cited. With reference to inductive ITs, their main issue is the iron core non-linearity that makes them introduce errors up to some percents in the measurement of harmonics. For this reason, at the moment this paper is written, two methods are the most acknowledged for the accurate characterization of inductive ITs [18], [20]. Both the methods involve realistic waveforms (that are waveforms very similar to actual power system waveforms) composed by the fundamental component at rated frequency and amplitude, plus other harmonic components with reduced amplitudes. The first method [18] (in the following named also

FH1, that stands for Fundamental plus 1 Harmonic tone), includes also one sweeping harmonic tone, whereas the second method [20] (in the following named also FHN, that stands for Fundamental plus N Harmonic tones), includes also a number of harmonic tones having random amplitudes and phase angles.

Both these methods involve the generation of a quite high number of waveforms, in the order of $\sim 100 - 1000$, depending on the frequency range of interest as well as the required accuracy. Thus, they require a significant time, in the order of $\sim 1 - 10$ hours, for the characterization of a single IT. Therefore, they can result unsuitable for the industrial laboratories, where the use of time-consuming techniques represents a bottleneck and then, by extension, a cost.

In this framework, the European research project EMPiR 19NRM05 IT4PQ [27]-[28] aims at identifying proper characterization methods and test conditions for VTs, employed for PQ measurements, to be performed in primary as well as in the industrial laboratories; the work here presented is part of this project.

The study presented in [26] analyses PQ phenomena that can impact on the performance of IT. The next step, which is objective of this paper, is the investigation among these phenomena of a novel test waveform designed for the fast and accurate frequency characterization of VT. This waveform is properly chosen in order to meet three features: 1) it is a realistic and already well standardized waveform, 2) it has the same periodicity as the fundamental tone and 3) it exhibits a uniform spectral content within the specified frequency range of interest. To achieve this goal, an Oscillatory Transient (OT) composed by a Fundamental Tone plus a Damped Oscillatory Waveform (FDOW) has been identified. The DOWs, described in [8], are a transient phenomenon with a wide frequency spectrum [29], [30] that originate in power systems, for instance, following a capacitor bank or a line energization. The generated DOW waveforms have a primary component frequency lower than 5 kHz and a duration from 0.3 ms to 50 ms [8], [30]. Due to their frequent presence in power systems, the DOW waveforms are used for the immunity test of MV equipment [31] and tests for relays and relays system associated with electric power apparatus [32]. Another important feature of the DOWs is the fact that they can be quite easily generated through a generator simpler than those used for FH1 and FHN tests; a circuit composed by a number of passive components, namely resistors, capacitors and inductors, opportunely sized, one or more switches and a power frequency or a Direct Current (DC) generator, as shown, for instance, in [33], [34], can be used. All the cited features make DOWs very promising for a fast and accurate frequency characterization of VTs to be performed in industrial laboratories.

In this paper, the use of DOWs for the fast characterization of inductive VTs is analysed. It is important to underline that, although DOWs can be generated through circuits like those shown in [33], [34], the scope of this paper is not to validate a circuit for the generation of DOWs. The scope of this paper is just to analyse the possibility to employ DOWs for the fast frequency characterization of inductive VTs. Therefore, general purpose generation and measurement setups were used for this

scope. To validate the proposed method, the results obtained with the DOWs method are compared with those obtained using FH1 [18] and FHN [20], considered as the reference methods. Since FH1 and FHN are considered as the reference methods, in the rest of the paper the word “accurate”, referred to proposed method, means that the proposed method gives results compatible with those obtained with FH1 and FHN.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the DOW test waveform and Section III provides guidelines on the selection of the DOW parameters, following analytical as well as physical considerations. Section IV introduces a slightly modified version of the DOW test waveform. Section V and Section VI describe two different generation and measurement setups and the test procedures adopted to prove the feasibility of the proposed method. In Section VII and Section VIII extensive experimental results are provided and discussed and, finally, Section IX draws the conclusions.

II. THE PROPOSED TEST WAVEFORM

The basic test waveform to employ in IT accuracy evaluation, according to international standards [9]-[12], is a virtually pure sine waveform having rated frequency (50/60 Hz) and amplitude. However, in order to evaluate the IT accuracy at other frequencies, more complex waveforms are needed [13]-[26]. All these authors agree on a general requirement: the use of realistic waveforms in the IT characterization. In fact, especially for inductive ITs, the measurement accuracy can be better evaluated only if they are tested in conditions similar to the actual operating conditions, due to their non-linear behaviour. With reference to inductive IT, [22] shows that it is possible to predict the accuracy in the measurement of a transient phenomenon starting from the accuracy at harmonic frequencies. FH1 and FHN tests require the use of a quite high number of waveforms, in the order of $\sim 100 - 1000$, thus requiring a significant time, in the order of $\sim 1 - 10$ hours, for the characterization of a single IT. Therefore, this paper, starting from the requirement of using a realistic waveform, analyses the possibility to use a different waveform with the aim to make the IT characterization process faster. The proposed waveform is composed by a fundamental tone, having rated amplitude and frequency (50/60 Hz), and a DOW, namely a damped sinusoidal component, having a higher frequency and a reduced amplitude. One period of this waveform is described by equation (1),

$$y(t) = \sqrt{2}A_1 \sin(2\pi f_1 t) + \sqrt{2}A_d e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \sin[2\pi f_d(t-t_0) + \phi_d] u(t-t_0), \quad (1)$$

where:

- A_1 and f_1 , are, respectively, the rated Root Mean Square (RMS) amplitude and frequency of the fundamental component;
- A_d , f_d and ϕ_d are, respectively, RMS amplitude, frequency and initial phase angles of the DOW;
- α is the damping factor, strictly greater than zero;
- $u(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside step function;
- t_0 is a positive time between zero and the length of the period of the fundamental component and represents the start time of the DOW within the fundamental period.

In (1), the expression of the DOW is taken from [30] according to the mathematical modelling of many transient phenomena, the waveform of DOW is expressed as exponentially decaying sinusoids. For sake of clarity and simplicity, in this section t_0 is chosen as equal to zero. In section III.E, some considerations on t_0 will be shown. In the rest of the paper, a waveform expressed by equation (1) will be referred to as FDOW (Fundamental plus a DOW).

The Fourier transform of the FDOW is described by (2):

$$Y(f) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2j} A_1 [\delta(f - f_1) - \delta(f + f_1)] + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2j} A_d \left(\frac{e^{j\phi_d}}{\alpha + j2\pi(f - f_d)} - \frac{e^{-j\phi_d}}{\alpha + j2\pi(f + f_d)} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function.

Unlike the purely sinusoidal case, $Y(f)$ has all the frequency components; moreover, considering the portion of the spectrum given by the DOW, the magnitude peak is obtained exactly when $f = \pm f_d$. These properties can be seen in the graphical representation of (1) and of the magnitude of (2), shown, respectively, in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b. The following choices of the parameters were done:

- $A_1 = 1 \text{ p.u.}$, $f_1 = 50 \text{ Hz}$;
- $A_d = 0.5 \text{ p.u.}$, $f_d = 1.2 \text{ kHz}$, $\phi_d = 0.13 \text{ rad}$, $\alpha = 2000 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $t_0 = 0$

In order to make the FDOW suitable for VT characterization, it should have a periodicity equal to that of the fundamental component. Therefore, if a DOW is added, every period, to the fundamental component, equation (1) becomes (3):

Fig. 1. One period (a) of the FDOW and its magnitude spectrum (b).

$$y(t) = \sqrt{2} A_1 \sin(2\pi f_1 t) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \sqrt{2} A_d e^{-\alpha(t-T_k)} \sin[2\pi f_d(t - T_k) + \phi_d] u(t - T_k), \quad (3)$$

where:

$$T_k = (t_0 + k/f_1) \quad (4)$$

Moreover, in the rest of the paper, for sake of clarity, instead of t_0 , we will refer to the quantity γ , related to t_0 as in (5):

$$\gamma = 2\pi f_1 t_0 \quad (5)$$

The quantity γ represents a phase angle referred to the fundamental component. In particular, it represents the fundamental phase angle at which the DOW starts. The use of γ allows to disengage from the fundamental frequency and, moreover, in the authors' opinion, it is a more intuitive quantity with respect to t_0 . With an abuse of language, the quantity γ will be referred to as the start phase angle of the DOW.

III. ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTS OF THE DOW PARAMETERS CHOICE

The spectrum of the FDOW depends on the choice of the DOW parameters, i.e., damping factor, amplitude, frequency, phase angle and γ . This section analyses how changes to these parameters affect the FDOW spectrum.

A. Phase Angle of the DOW: effect on the DC component

It can be easily demonstrated that FDOW signal has a DC component, since the exponential decay leads to an asymmetry between the positive and negative DOW half-waves. Having a DC component is really undesirable, since it can lead the transformers to saturate. Therefore, if a measurement setup including a step-up transformer is used, the presence of the DC component at its input will make it introduce significant spurious harmonics, so introducing undesired distortion of the test waveform. Even if the measurement setup uses a MV amplifier to supply the test waveform to the inductive VT under test, a DC component could lead the VT to saturation and so to invalidate the test.

The DC component of the DOW can be evaluated starting with equation (6):

$$Y(0) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2j} A_d \left(\frac{e^{j\phi_d}}{\alpha - j2\pi f_d} - \frac{e^{-j\phi_d}}{\alpha + j2\pi f_d} \right) \quad (6)$$

In (6), the two terms in brackets are complex conjugate. Thus, their difference is an imaginary number and it is twice their imaginary part, given by (7):

$$Y(0) = \sqrt{2} A_d \frac{\alpha \sin \phi_d + 2\pi f_d \cos \phi_d}{\alpha^2 + (2\pi f_d)^2} \quad (7)$$

To provide a signal with no DC component, the phase angle ϕ_d of DOW has to be chosen such that the numerator of (7) is equal to zero. Therefore, it is easy to show that the required value is given by the equation (8):

$$\phi_d = -\tan^{-1}(2\pi f_d / \alpha) \quad (8)$$

B. Start phase angle of the DOW

The choice of the start phase angle γ of the DOW could introduce significant changes in the accuracy of an inductive VT evaluated by using a FDOW. In order to better understand its role, in the following, a brief recall of the operation of an inductive VT is done.

According to Faraday's law [35], when an input voltage is supplied to the primary winding of an inductive VT, it produces a proportional magnetic flux inside the iron core. This has a non-linear behaviour, that influences the metrological performances of the VT and depends on the amplitude of the magnetic flux, which, in turns, depends on the supplied voltage amplitude. FH1 and FHN waveforms are basically a sum of steady-state sinewaves, namely the fundamental and the harmonic components. Considering one period of this kind of waveforms, the magnetic flux generated by the harmonic components is always present, for every value of the magnetic flux generated by the fundamental tone. Therefore, when the accuracy of the VT is evaluated at a harmonic frequency, by analysing a time frame equal to an integer number of periods of the fundamental tone, the obtained values represent a kind of a mean value over all the values of the magnetic flux generated by the fundamental tone.

Differently from FH1 and FHN waveforms, one period of a FDOW is the sum of a fundamental tone and a transient event, with a duration quite smaller than the fundamental period (see for instance Fig. 1a). Therefore, in this case, when the accuracy of the VT is evaluated at a harmonic frequency, by analysing a time frame equal to an integer number of periods of the fundamental tone, the obtained values represent a kind of a mean value over only a small portion of values of the magnetic flux generated by the fundamental tone. Thus, standing the non-linear behaviour of the VT, the position of the DOW inside the fundamental period can have a big influence on the obtained accuracy at a harmonic frequency. For sake of more clarity, consider also the two following cases.

- 1) When γ is equal to zero, the DOW starts in correspondence of the positive zero crossing of the fundamental tone. In this case, for the entire duration of the DOW, the most important contribution to the total magnetic flux is given by the DOW. From the point of view of the obtained accuracy at harmonic frequencies, this situation produces results very similar to a FH1 or a FHN waveform having a very small fundamental component, far from its rated value. Literature [36]-[37] shows that in this way the obtained results are not accurate.
- 2) When γ is equal to $\pi/2$ rad, the DOW waveform starts in correspondence of the peak value of the fundamental tone. In this case, for the entire duration of the DOW, the total flux is very high, as it is given by the peak of the fundamental flux and by the DOW flux. Also in this case, the obtained results could be inaccurate as the VT under test can reach the saturation.

These considerations have highlighted that the choice of γ is very important in order to obtain accurate results in the VT characterization by using FDOW. It follows that a reasonable value of γ may be around $\pi/4$ or $3\pi/4$. In Section VII, the best value of γ will be experimentally determined.

C. Damping factor of the DOW

The damping factor α of the DOW is the inverse of the decay time τ of the waveform. The possible range of variation of α is established starting from the typical DOW duration outlined in IEEE 1159 [8] and then narrowing it down. The decision to restrict this range is driven by the need to maintain the periodicity of the FDOW equal to those of the sole fundamental tone. To achieve this, it is crucial that at the end of every period of the fundamental tone, the amplitude of the superimposed DOW is negligible compared to the measurement uncertainty. This constrain is verified by considering that after about twenty times τ , the amplitude of the DOW can be considered zero (within $1 \mu\text{V}/\text{V}$), so the maximum value of the time constant τ is fixed to 1 ms. Consequently, α has a minimum limit value of 1000 s^{-1} .

Choosing this minimum value of α implies that the amplitudes of the spectral components in the range $[f_d - 500, f_d + 500] \text{ Hz}$ are quite higher than the amplitudes outside this range. In fact, the tones outside this range are quite overlapped with constant amplitudes, independently from the values of the α . It is worth recalling that one of the features of the novel test waveform should be the near uniformity of its amplitude spectrum. This condition is also suggested by the standards about grid voltage characteristics, e.g. [2], which establish consistent and quite similar limits for harmonics beyond the 13th order.

Therefore, the desired features of quite uniformity of the magnitude spectrum of the test waveform can be satisfied as the α parameter increases. However, it is not possible to arbitrarily increase this parameter, since, approaching the upper limit, the amplitudes of the produced spectral tones can reach low values implying higher uncertainty contributions. For these reasons the α value is chosen as 2000 s^{-1} .

D. Amplitude of the DOW

According to equation (2), the amplitude A_d of the DOW essentially influences the amplitude of the harmonic tones of the FDOW spectrum. Moreover, the FDOW magnitude spectrum has a peak at $f = f_d$, whereas the amplitude rapidly decreases moving away from f_d . In particular, the minimum amplitude value is obtained at the limit frequencies (not considering the fundamental component) of the range of interest. Moreover, it has to be considered that no indications about harmonic amplitudes to use in the tests are provided by international standards on ITs. Therefore, a possible criterion to choose the minimum value of A_d , can come from the minimum desired amplitude of the harmonic components at the limits of the frequency range of interest of the tests.

For what concerns the maximum value of A_d , the limit can be imposed by the used instrumentation. In particular, according to [11], the accuracy of VTs at fundamental frequency must be evaluated by varying the amplitude of the fundamental component between 80 % and 120 % of the rated value. Typically, calibration laboratories have the capabilities to generate at least the 130 % of the rated fundamental amplitude. According to Section III.B, γ should be chosen in such a way that the peak amplitude of the FDOW is significantly lower than the sum of the peak amplitudes of the fundamental tone and of the DOW.

Following these considerations, a reasonable range of variation for A_d is between 5 % and 50 % of the fundamental amplitude.

E. Frequency of the DOW

The frequency f_d of the DOW (see equation (2)) is another parameter that influences the amplitude of the FDO spectrum at the limits of the frequency range of interest of the tests and, therefore, determines the width of the range itself.

According to [4], the basic time frame to use for harmonic analysis is equal to 10 cycles of fundamental waveform. Considering the case of a 50 Hz power system, this time frame is equal to 200 ms, giving a frequency resolution of 5 Hz. Theoretically, it is possible to choose the f_d value equal to any integer multiple of 5 Hz, including a harmonic frequency of the fundamental tone. In this case, the DOW spectrum has all the harmonic components, including a component at fundamental frequency, superimposed to the fundamental tone of the test. Moreover, since the DOW magnitude spectrum exponentially decreases, the first harmonics up to the 10th harmonic order can have an amplitude comparable with the spurious harmonics introduced by the fundamental tone, that are a source of errors. Therefore, in order to reduce the errors, a compensation technique, like SINDICOMP [18] or HD [20], should be used. However, in these cases, the number of tests increase.

To summarize, a possible option for the value of f_d involves the selection of a harmonic or interharmonic frequency that halves the selected characterization bandwidth of the VT. In such a way, the average amplitude of the harmonic tones, inside the frequency range of interest, is maximized.

F. Ranges of variation of the DOW parameters

Following the considerations given in this section, Table I gives the ranges of variation of the DOW parameters. These values are given, without loss of generality, with reference to a 50 Hz power system.

IV. A DOW INTRODUCING INTERHARMONIC COMPONENTS

Consider a particular FDO including a DOW with the frequency f_d equal to a harmonic component of the fundamental tone and with an arbitrary value of the phase angle ϕ_d , provided that it increases of π at each period of the fundamental component, as in equation (9).

$$y(t) = \sqrt{2}A_1 \sin(2\pi f_1 t) + \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} \sqrt{2}A_d e^{-\alpha(t-T_k)} \sin[2\pi h f_1 (t - T_k) + \phi_d + k\pi] u(t - T_k), \quad (9)$$

where h is an integer number at least 10 times higher than 1. In this case, the periodicity of the FDO is equal to two cycles of the fundamental component. Therefore, theoretically,

TABLE I: SUGGESTED RANGES OF VARIATION OF DOW PARAMETERS

Parameters	Min value	Max value
α (s^{-1})	Close to 2000	
γ (rad)	Close to $\pi/4$	
ϕ_d (rad)	According to equation (8)	
f_d (Hz)	Harmonic, or harmonic ± 25 Hz, that halves the selected characterization bandwidth of the VT.	
A_d (p.u.)	5% of A_1	50% of A_1

considering a 50 Hz power system, the spectrum of this waveform, obtained by analysing a time frame of 200 ms, should contain tones every 25 Hz, thus harmonics but also interharmonics of the fundamental component. However, due to the particular symmetry of the DOWs in two consecutive periods, the even harmonics of the 25 Hz tone, including the DC component, are zero; therefore, other than the 25 Hz tone and the fundamental tone at 50 Hz, the spectrum contains only the odd harmonics of the 25 Hz component, that are interharmonics for the fundamental tone at 50 Hz.

A great advantage of this waveform is the fact that the introduced interharmonic components do not superimpose to the spurious harmonics due to the fundamental tone, and, therefore, no compensation techniques or other supplementary tests are required for their accurate evaluation. Moreover, we can assume a very similar behaviour of the VT between two adjacent harmonic frequencies. Therefore, if the VT is characterized by using this particular FDO that introduces all the interharmonic components multiple of 25 Hz, the VT behaviour at harmonic frequencies can be obtained by interpolation between two adjacent interharmonic tones.

In conclusion, the use of the DOW that introduces interharmonic tones seems the best candidate for the accuracy evaluation of VTs, since: 1) structurally, no DC component is introduced (whatever the value of ϕ_d) and 2) no compensation technique nor supplementary tests are required since no harmonic components are introduced.

In the rest of the paper, these kinds of waveforms will be referred to as FIDOW (Fundamental plus Interharmonic DOW). In Sections VI, VII and VIII both FDO as well as FIDOW will be extensively analysed and the related results compared to those obtained with FH1 and FHN tests.

V. MEASUREMENT SETUP

To experimentally evaluate and demonstrate the validity of the proposed characterisation technique, two measurement setups are developed at the Università degli Studi della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli" (SUN) and Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM).

The generation and measurement setup of SUN is shown in Fig. 2a. The reference voltage signal to be applied to the VTs under test is provided by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) National Instrument (NI) PCI eXtension Instrumentation (PXI) 5422 (16 bit, variable output gain, ± 12 V output range, 200 MHz maximum sampling rate, and 256 MB of onboard memory).

The AWG generates a 4 MHz clock that is used to derive the sampling clock; this allows obtaining coherent sampling, thus avoiding spectral leakage. Acquisition of the primary and secondary waveforms of the VT under test has been performed with a multifunction I/O module PXIe-6124 (± 10 V, 16 bit, maximum sampling rate of 4 MHz). Waveforms have been sampled with a 1 MHz rate. The output of the AWG is connected to an Arbitrary four-quadrant voltage and current amplifier Bolab (± 75 V, 40 A, 1 kW, DC – 1 MHz) feeding the VT under test through a 100 V / 24 kV step-up transformer.

Primary voltages are scaled with a commercial divider OhmLab KV-10A (High-Voltage Divider, HVD) having a ratio of 1000 V/V and uncertainties on ratio and phase errors of,

respectively, $180 \mu\text{V/V}$ and $190 \mu\text{rad}$ (level of confidence 95%) from DC up to 4 kHz. A low voltage divider (LVD), having a ratio of about 18.5 V/V and uncertainties on ratio and phase errors of, respectively, $100 \mu\text{V/V}$ and $110 \mu\text{rad}$ (level of confidence 95%) from DC up to 4 kHz, has been designed and built for measuring the secondary voltage of the VT. Calibration of HVD and the LVD was performed at INRIM. The overall uncertainty (level of confidence 95%) of the measurement setup is lower than $300 \mu\text{V/V}$ and $300 \mu\text{rad}$ for the measurement of the ratio error and the phase error, respectively, from DC up to 4 kHz (see Table II).

The reference generation and measurement setup of INRIM is depicted in Fig. 2b.

The voltage signals are generated by the Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG) National Instrument (NI) PCI eXtension for Instrumentation (PXI) 5421, with 16 bit, variable output gain, $\pm 12\text{V}$ output range, 100 MHz maximum sampling rate, 256 MB of onboard memory. The AWG is housed in a PXI chassis and its 10 MHz PXI clock is used as a reference clock for the PLL circuitry. Another AWG is employed to generate a 12.8 MHz clock, which is provided as a time base clock to the acquisition system.

The low voltage waveform generated by the AWG is amplified by a Trek high-voltage power amplifier ($\pm 30\text{ kV}$, $\pm 20\text{ mA}$, 20 kHz). The applied MV voltage values are scaled by a reference resistive-capacitive voltage divider (30 kV, DC to 12 kHz) designed, built and characterized at INRIM [25].

The acquisition system is composed by a NI compact Data Acquisition system (cDAQ) chassis with various input modules having 24 bit resolution, 50 kHz maximum sampling rate and input range from $\pm 500\text{ mV}$ up to $\pm 425\text{ V}$. The uncertainty (level of confidence 95 %) of the ratio and phase errors up to 9 kHz is $250 \mu\text{V/V}$ and $300 \mu\text{rad}$, respectively (see Table III).

It is worth noting that an alternative method to analyse and compare the outputs of the reference and the under test sensors is based on the use of a differential measuring system, as shown in [38].

VI. DESCRIPTION OF THE TESTS

In all the performed tests, the waveforms have been analysed by performing the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) over a time frames of 10 cycles of the fundamental component, as suggested by [3] for the measurement of harmonics.

TABLE II: EXPANDED UNCERTAINTY (LEVEL OF CONFIDENCE 95 %) ASSOCIATED TO THE MEASUREMENT OF RATIO AND PHASE ERROR USING THE TWO EXPERIMENTAL SETUPS

		Frequency (Hz)			
	SUN	50	500	1500	4000
Ratio error ($\mu\text{V/V}$)	90	150	220	300	
Phase error (μrad)	100	170	250	300	
		INRIM			
	50	1000	5000	9000	
Ratio error ($\mu\text{V/V}$)	70	100	180	250	
Phase error (μrad)	70	130	220	300	

Fig. 2. Generation and Measurement setup for VT characterization at SUN (a) and INRIM (b)

The accuracy of the of VTs under test at harmonic frequencies is evaluated by calculating the harmonic ratio and phase errors, through the equations (10) and (11):

$$\varepsilon_h = \frac{k_r V_{s,h} - V_{p,h}}{V_{p,h}} \quad (10)$$

$$\varphi_h = \varphi_{s,h} - \varphi_{p,h} \quad (11)$$

where:

- $k_r = V_{p,r}/V_{s,r}$ is the rated transformation ratio ($V_{p,r}$ and $V_{s,r}$ are the rated primary and secondary voltages);
- $V_{p,h}$ and $V_{s,h}$ are the RMS values of the primary and secondary h -order harmonic voltages;
- $\varphi_{p,h}$ and $\varphi_{s,h}$ are the phase angles of the primary and secondary h -order harmonic voltages.

Equations (10) and (11) are a frequency extension of ratio and phase errors defined for fundamental frequency [23]. Two commercial inductive VTs for 50 Hz MV power systems, whose main features are shown in TABLE III, were tested. In particular, VT_A is tested at SUN, whereas VT_B is tested at INRIM.

A. Reference tests

As highlighted in Section I, FH1 [18] and FHN [20] tests are assumed as the reference methods for the accuracy evaluation of VTs at the harmonic frequencies. That is, the values of ratio and phase errors at the harmonic frequencies of a VT obtained with these tests are considered the reference values. The parameters of reference tests are shown in Table VI. Moreover,

TABLE III: VTs UNDER TEST PARAMETERS

VT	Accuracy Class	Primary Voltage (kV)	Secondary Voltage (V)	Rated Burden (VA)
VT _A	0.5	3	100	25
VT _B	0.5	20/ $\sqrt{3}$	100/ $\sqrt{3}$	30

for each tests the fundamental amplitude A_1 is fixed equal to the rated primary voltage of the VTs under test.

It is worth noting that the VTs under test are preliminarily characterized with a sinusoidal waveform having the rated frequency and amplitude. This preliminary test is necessary to apply the SINDICOMP technique [18] to the results obtained with FH1 and FHN tests, in order to mitigate the non-linearity errors introduced by the inductive VTs due to the presence of the fundamental component.

Basically, SINDICOMP consists in: 1) measure the VT secondary voltage harmonic phasors in the preliminary sinusoidal test and 2) use them as a correction for the spurious harmonic tones produced in the output voltage in the tests with distorted waveforms.

A detailed description of SINDICOMP can be found in [18] whereas [25] deepen FH1 and FHN tests, their comparison and the application of SINDICOMP to both.

B. FDOWN and FIDOW tests

In all the FDOWN and FIDOW tests, the fundamental amplitude is equal to the rated primary voltage of the VTs under test and the fundamental frequency is 50 Hz. Several tests were performed to analyse the effects of the variation of FDOWN and FIDOW parameters on the VT accuracy evaluation through the new proposed procedure. All the obtained results are compared with those obtained with FH1 and FHN tests. Section VII and Section VIII deeply discusses the experimental results.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS: IMPACT OF THE DOW PARAMETERS

First of all, the impact of the DOW parameters (γ , f_d , A_d) on the evaluation of the VTs frequency behaviour is analysed, in Sections from VII.A to VII.C. They are chosen as indicated in Table V. Then, a comparison among the responses obtained with FDOWN and FIDOW is provided in Section VII.D, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of both the approaches. For sake of brevity and clarity, for these analyses, reference will be made only to ratio error.

A. Effects of the start phase angle of the DOW

Fig. 3 shows various ratio errors (see (10)) of VT_A, from the 20th to the 80th harmonic order, obtained with FDOWN, by varying γ (fixing A_d and f_d as in Table V and ϕ_d as in (8)), and with FHN. For the FHN test also the $\pm 95\%$ ratio error variation

TABLE IV: REFERENCE TEST PARAMETERS

Test	Harmonic amplitude (% of A_1)	Harmonic phase (rad)	Number of tests
FH1	1%	0	>500
FHN	From 0.5% up to 1%	From $-\pi$ up to π	>1000

range, along with the uncertainty (level of confidence 95 %), is shown. This range of variation is obtained for an intrinsic reason. Each FHN [25] waveform has all the harmonic components but with random amplitudes and phase angles. The inductive VTs, due to the intrinsic non-linear effects, have a harmonic behaviour that depends on the particular waveform. In other words, stimulating a VT with M different waveforms (see Table IV), M different frequency behaviours will be obtained. Fig. 3 shows, thus, the ratio error mean value curve and the two curves equal to the $\pm 95\%$ of the ratio error variation range plus the uncertainty (level of confidence 95 %). The bars on the FDOWN curves in Fig. 3 represent the uncertainty (level of confidence 95 %).

In the rest of the paper, the uncertainty (level of confidence 95 %) is included both in the $\pm 95\%$ limits as well as in the error bars.

Looking at Fig. 3, when γ is zero, the harmonic ratio error exceeds the FHN $\pm 95\%$ range, whereas when γ is close to $\pi/4$ rad, the harmonic ratio error curve is close to the reference FHN curve. In this respect, Fig. 3 graphically represents what is theoretically explained in Section III.B.

To better explain this effect, consider Fig 4. Fig. 4a (Fig. 4b) reports the ratio error of VT_A (VT_B) at the 40th (60th) harmonic order, obtained by varying γ . Fig 4a and Fig. 4b also report the FHN ratio error, both the mean value as well as the 95 % limits, at the related harmonic frequency.

First, it can be observed that there is a periodicity of π rad of the ratio error versus γ : this result confirms that γ is strictly related to the flux operating conditions of the VT.

For both the tested VTs, selecting a γ value near to the zero crossing of the fundamental tone (i.e., 0 or π rad) provides results not compatible with the FHN results. Also, the selection of γ near to $\pi/2$ rad, that is near the maximum values of the fundamental components, can lead to results not compatible with FHN results.

Another interesting phenomenon to observe is the fact that, for both the VTs, when γ is equal to $k\pi$ rad the obtained curves are always lower than the lower limit of the FHN range. This behaviour is always observed when the VT harmonic ratio errors are evaluated with a frequency sweep of sine waves having amplitudes quite lower than the rated VT voltage. This phenomenon is highlighted also in [36]-[37].

TABLE V: DOW TEST PARAMETERS

VT _A				
Parameters	Range	Step	Fixed Quantities	# Tests
γ (rad)	$[0, 2\pi[$	$\pi/10$	$A_d = 50\%$ $f_d = 1.5$ kHz	20
f_d (kHz)	$[0.3, 3.9]$	400	$\gamma = 0$ rad $A_d = 50\%$	10
A_d (%)	5, 20, 50	-	$\gamma = 4\pi/5$ rad $f_d = 1.5$ kHz	3
VT _B				
Parameters	Range	Step	Fixed Quantities	# Tests
γ (rad)	$[0, \pi]$	$\pi/12$	$A_d = 30\%$ $f_d = 3$ kHz	13
f_d (kHz)	$[0.5, 4]$	-	$\gamma = \pi/4$ rad $A_d = 30\%$	4
A_d (%)	10, 20, 30	-	$\gamma = \pi/6$ rad $f_d = 3$ kHz	3

These considerations highlight two important aspects about the choice of γ . The first is that, thanks to the periodicity of γ , there are four intervals, contained in one period $[0, 2\pi]$ rad of the fundamental tone, that ensure accurate results: they are the intervals around $\pi/4 + k\pi/2$, with k being an integer number, that is $[\pi/6 + k\pi/2, \pi/3 + k\pi/2]$ rad. However, due to the considerations shown in Section III.C, related to the duration of the DOW, only the intervals in the first half period of the fundamental tone should be chosen. The second aspect is that it is not important to choose a specific γ for each VT under test, since every value in the cited ranges gives accurate results. This aspect, in particular, gives flexibility and versatility to the presented characterization method.

B. Effects of the amplitude of the DOW

The choice of the DOW amplitude A_d directly impacts on the amplitude of the produced harmonic tones. The lower is the DOW amplitude, the lower are the harmonic tones amplitudes, especially at harmonic frequencies far from f_d . Fig. 5 reports VT_A ratio errors measured at different harmonic frequencies by varying A_d (f_d and γ are chosen as in Table V and ϕ_d as in (8)). It can be observed that reducing A_d produces results affected by a higher uncertainty, in the order of some percent. In particular, the higher uncertainty is observed for A_d equal to 5% and for $h = 10$ and $h = 70$ that are, in Fig. 5, the harmonic tones farther from f_d . This is due to measurement problems related to the necessity of measuring simultaneously harmonic components with amplitudes in the order of ~ 1 mV and the fundamental tone with an amplitude of 3 kV. On the contrary, for $h=30$ that is the frequency of the DOW, also the result obtained for $A_d = 5\%$ is affected by quite a low uncertainty, compared to the uncertainty obtained for $A_d = 5\%$ at the other harmonic orders, and the mean values measured under the three A_d conditions are well overlapped within a deviation of 0.1%.

Fig. 6a (Fig. 6b) shows the ratio error of VT_B at the 50th (60th) harmonic order, with $f_d = 3$ kHz, $\gamma = \pi/6$ rad, ϕ_d as in (8) and three different values of A_d , 10%, 20% and 30%; FHN results are also reported. Similarly to what found for VT_A , increasing the A_d value, the uncertainty of the ratio error decreases. For $h = 60$, that is equal to f_d , the results obtained with the three A_d are within the $\pm 95\%$ FHN range. For $h = 50$, even if all the FDOV mean values are well overlapped with the FHN mean value, the uncertainty obtained for $A_d = 10\%$ is higher than the FHN range limits.

So, as expected, increasing the A_d values ensures more accurate measurements over the entire considered frequency range.

C. Effects of the frequency of the DOW

Fig. 7a (Fig. 7b) shows the ratio errors of VT_A (VT_B) measured at a fixed harmonic tone, $h = 40$ ($h = 60$), obtained with FDOV, by varying f_d (fixing A_d and γ as in Table V and ϕ_d as in (8)), and with FHN.

Looking at Fig. 7a, it can be observed that, for all the cases, ε_{40} is compatible with the reference value. In particular, for $f_d = 2$ kHz, that is $h=40$, the mean value of the ratio errors obtained with FDOV and with FHN are perfectly overlapped and the deviations are within $\pm 0.1\%$. For f_d values that differ most from $h=40$, both the difference between the FDOV and FHN mean values, as well as the FDOV deviations, increase.

Fig. 3. VT_A ratio error at harmonic order h , obtained with: 1) FDOV with amplitude equal to 50%, frequency equal to 1.5 kHz and various γ (dot, up-triangle and down-triangle markers); 2) FHN (mean value with diamond markers and ± 95 limits with square markers).

Fig. 4. Ratio error of VT_A in Fig. 4a (VT_B in Fig. 4b) at harmonic order $h=40$ ($h=60$), obtained with: 1) FDOV with f_d equal to 1.5 kHz (3 kHz) and various γ (dot markers); 2) FHN (mean value with diamond markers and ± 95 limits with square markers).

This result is explained considering that the 40th harmonic tone has a low amplitude when f_d moves away from 2 kHz.

Very similar considerations can be done for VT_B , looking at Fig. 7b.

This result suggests that f_d should be chosen as the half of the upper limit of the frequency range in which the VT has to be characterized.

Fig. 5. VT_A ratio error at harmonic order h , obtained with FIDOW with f_d and γ equal to 1.5 kHz and $4\pi/5$ rad, respectively, and various A_d values.

Fig. 6. VT_B ratio error at harmonic order $h=50$ (a) and $h=60$ (b), obtained with FIDOW with f_d and γ equal to 3 kHz and $\pi/6$ rad, respectively, and various A_d values.

D. Comparison of FIDOW and FIDOW results

As it said in Section IV, the FIDOW is a very promising waveform, since, compared to the FIDOW does not introduce the DC component and does not require a non-linearity compensation technique. However, it introduces interharmonics instead of harmonics. Therefore, in order to use FIDOW to evaluate the VT accuracy at harmonic frequencies,

we have to prove that the information on the VT behaviour obtained with FIDOW and FIDOW are equivalent.

For this analysis, both the FIDOW as well as the FIDOW waveforms have the same values for the parameters f_d , A_d , γ and ϕ_d . The ratio errors of VT_A are shown in Fig. 8, where $f_d = 1.5$ kHz, $A_d = 50\%$ of A_1 , $\gamma = 4\pi/5$ rad and ϕ_d is chosen as in (8). Instead, the ratio errors VT_B are shown in Fig. 9a, where $f_d = 3$ kHz, $A_d = 30\%$ of A_1 , $\gamma = \pi/4$ rad and ϕ_d is chosen as in (8).

Very similar considerations can be done for the two VTs. Excluding the ratio error values until 500 Hz, that is until the 10th harmonic order, the FIDOW and FIDOW approaches yield overlapping results with maximum deviations of $\pm 0.1\%$ for VT_A and $\pm 0.05\%$ for VT_B . Fig. 9b shows the difference between the FIDOW and FIDOW ratio errors of VT_B from the 20th up to the 100th harmonic order.

However, including the lower frequencies, deviations are higher than some percents. These differences are due to non-linear effects at harmonic frequencies, which are highlighted by the FIDOW test but not by the FIDOW test. In particular, FIDOW waveforms with f_d quite higher than 1 kHz provide to the VT under test primary harmonics with low amplitudes ($<0.1\%$), which can be directly compared to the spurious tones generated by the VT due to the presence of the fundamental component [18]. These spurious tones can be

Fig. 7. Ratio error of VT_A in Fig. 7a (VT_B in Fig. 7b) at harmonic order $h=40$ ($h=60$), obtained with: 1) FIDOW (dot markers), with A_d and γ equal to 50% and $4\pi/5$ (30% and $\pi/4$), respectively, and various f_d values; 2) FHN (mean value with diamond markers and ± 95 limits with square markers).

compensated by applying non-linearity compensation techniques known in the literature, such as SINDICOMP [18] or HD [20]. The application of SINDICOMP leads to a quite smoother behaviour until the first harmonic frequencies, with ratio and phase error values close to those at 50 Hz. Looking at experimental results, it is evident that a response exhibiting these characteristics (quite flat up to $h = 10$) is obtained with the FIDOW test, which, by its mathematical definition, does not introduce harmonics but rather interharmonics, which are not affected by the same non-linearities exhibited by the harmonics.

Therefore, the FIDOW test, although it introduces a slight complication in the test waveform (the phase changes every fundamental period by an amount equal to π) and requires to be analysed over time frames integer multiple of two fundamental periods, it does not require the use of a non-linearity compensation technique. Therefore, it provides results that can be directly compared with FH1 and FHN, provided that FH1 and FHN, as highlighted in Section VI.A, results have been compensated with a suitable non-linearity compensation technique.

Another advantage of both FIDOW and FIDOW tests is the possibility to measure the first resonance frequency of an inductive VT, as it can be seen in Fig. 9a, with a simple waveform. It is worth to note that this feature is, in principle, obtainable with a waveform containing all the harmonic components in the range of interest. However, with FIDOW and FIDOW, it is obtained with a waveform represented by a simple equation.

VIII. COMPARISON OF FIDOW WITH THE REFERENCE METHODS

This section presents a comparison among the VTs ratio and phase error responses obtained with the proposed FIDOW approach and with the reference methods, among the entire frequency range, that is up to 4 kHz for VT_A and 9 kHz for VT_B.

Fig. 10^a (Fig.10 b) shows the ratio (phase) errors of VT_A obtained with FH1, FHN and FIDOW.

Instead, Fig. 11^a (Fig.11 d) shows the ratio (phase) errors of VT_B obtained with FH1, FHN and FIDOW. Both for VT_A as well as for VT_B, FIDOW parameters have the same values of the test described in Section VII.D.

Fig. 11 b shows a zoom of Fig. 11a up to $h = 60$. For both the VTs, and for both ratio as well as phase errors, we can see that the FH1, FHN and FIDOW curves are well overlapped. The maximum deviations between the mean value curves of the FIDOW results and those obtained with FH1 and FHN are 0.2 % and 650 μ V/V for ratio errors, respectively for VT_A and VT_B, whereas they are 500 μ rad and 600 μ rad for phase errors, respectively for VT_A and VT_B.

In particular, Fig. 11c shows the deviation between the FIDOW and the FHN ratio errors up to the 110th harmonic order: the deviation is contained in the range of $\pm 650 \mu$ V/V.

IX. DISCUSSION ON THE MAIN RESULTS

The main outcomes of this paper can be summarized as follows.

A new realistic power system waveform, made by the superposition of a fundamental component and a periodic realistic transient (defined in the international standards about

Fig. 8. VT_A ratio errors at harmonic order h , obtained with FIDOW (square markers) and FIDOW (diamond markers), both having $f_d = 1.5$ kHz, $A_d = 50$ % of A_1 , $\gamma = 4\pi/5$ rad.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. (a) VT_B ratio errors at harmonic order h , obtained with FIDOW (square markers) and FIDOW (diamond markers), both having $f_d = 3$ kHz, $A_d = 30$ % of A_1 , $\gamma = \pi/4$ rad. (b) VT_B ratio error deviations among the mean values of FIDOW and FIDOW harmonic ratio errors.

power systems [8]), to use for the frequency characterization of inductive VTs, has been defined.

It has a wide spectrum, since contains all the harmonic, in the case of FIDOW, or the interharmonic (odd multiples of the half of the fundamental frequency), in case of FIDOW, components up to some kilohertz. In this way, with a single waveform it is possible to evaluate the frequency behaviour of a VT.

Since a VT can be characterized with a single waveform, the duration of the tests is strongly reduced to the order of ~ 1 s, whereas the most acknowledged procedures for frequency characterization of VTs, namely FH1 [18] and FHN [20], require a test duration in the order of $\sim 1-10$ hours. A deep theoretical and an experimental analysis has been conducted in

Fig. 10. Ratio (a) and phase (b) errors of VT_A versus harmonic order h obtained with: 1) FH1 (circle markers); 2) FHN (square markers); 3) FIDOW (cross markers) with A_d , f_d and γ equal to, respectively, 50 % of A_1 , 1.5 kHz and $4\pi/5$ rad.

order to choose the best values for the damped sine wave parameters.

The version of the waveform that produces only interharmonic components does not need the application of a non-linearity compensation technique, whereas FH1 and FHN require it.

Two different commercial MV VTs have been characterized with two different measurement setups. The frequency behaviours obtained with the proposed procedures have been compared with those obtained with the reference methods, that are FH1 and FHN, resulting compatible and showing maximum deviations among the mean values of 0.2 % and 600 μ rad, respectively for of ratio and phase errors, up to 9 kHz.

X. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a new waveform that allows to perform a fast frequency characterization of inductive VTs. It is a periodic waveform composed of a fundamental tone and a damped sine wave, that begins every period at the same fundamental tone phase angle and ends within the same period. The main outcomes of this paper are summarized in Section IX.

It is important to underline that these waveforms can be generated and measured by using the same measurement setups able to implement FH1 and FHN tests. In this respect it does not require additional features of the measurement setups. In addition, another advantage of the proposed waveform is the fact that it can be quite easily generated with a generator setup quite simpler than those required by FH1 and FHN tests. As shown, for instance, in [33], [34] a DOW can be generated through a circuit composed by a number of passive components, namely resistors, capacitors and inductors,

Fig. 11. Ratio (a) and phase (d) errors of VT_B versus harmonic order h obtained with: 1) FH1 (circle markers); 2) FHN (diamond markers); 3) FIDOW (square markers) with A_d , f_d and γ equal to, respectively, 30 % of A_1 , 3 kHz and $\pi/4$ rad. (b) shows a zoom of (a) up to $h = 60$. (c) shows the deviation between the FIDOW and the FHN ratio errors up to $h = 110$.

opportunistically sized, one or more switches and a power frequency or a DC generator. All these features make the proposed procedure attractive for the frequency characterization of inductive voltage transformers.

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